

Electrochemical studies on copper(II) complexes of ⁴N-alkyl/arylthiosemicarbazones and S-alkyl/aryldithiocarbazates of 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole

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Manuscript received 26 December 2006, accepted 5 January 2007

Abstract : The electrochemical behaviour of series of copper(II) complexes of pyrazolyl thiosemicarbazones and S-alkyl/aryl dithiocarbazates undergo a quasi-reversible one electron reduction in the range of -0.370 V to -0.480 V vs SCE; attributed to the copper(II)/copper(I) redox couple.

Keywords : Electrochemical study, copper(II), cyclic voltammetry.

In view of well documented antiviral activity of α -(N)-heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones and related dithiocarbazates¹ and the fact that the common mechanism of structural and biological properties of copper(II) heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones and S-alkyl/aryl dithiocarbazates is not yet fully understood². Sometime metal complexes especially those of copper(II) and iron(III) are found to be more active than uncomplexed thiosemicarbazones³. The enhanced biological activity of metal complexes has been under investigation for the last decades. This results prompts us to undertake cyclic voltammetric studies of copper(II) complexes as part of work^{4,5} for the synthesis and characterisation of some new thiosemicarbazones and S-alkyl/aryl dithiocarbazates of 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole-3-pyrrolidinylthiosemicarbazone (HMPzPyr), 5-methyl-3-formylpyrazole ⁴N-benzylthiosemicarbazone (HMPzNB) and S-benzyl- β -N-(5-methylpyrazole-3-yl)methylenedithiocarbazate (HMPzSB). Quasi-reversible copper(II)/copper(I) couples are observed for the reported complexes in the range of -0.370 V to -0.480 V.

R = ⁴N (HMPzPyr); R = ⁴NHCH₂Ph (HMPzNB); R = SCH₂Ph (HMPzSB)

Results and discussion

The electrochemical behaviour of heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones and related dithiocarbazates with sulphur and nitrogen donor atoms have been studied in order to monitor spectral, biological potentialities and structural changes accompanying electron transfer. Most have involved like complexes with disulphur chelating agents because of ease of reduction to their metal centres. The low ESR parameters (e.g. $g_{||}$) of the copper(II) complexes of heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones and dithiocarbazates are likely to be easily reducible. The results of our voltammetric studies of copper(II) complexes of HMPzPyr, HMPzNB and HMPzSB are summarized in Table 1 and the cyclic voltammograms of some representative complexes are shown in Fig. 1. The CV profiles of the present series of complexes are quite similar to those of the analogous complexes prepared with the related pyridinyl thiosemicarbazones^{6,7}. To facilitate discussion, all the reduction and oxidation peaks of the cyclic voltammograms have been identified and denoted by capitals letters. Close observation of repetitive scan profiles of the present complexes reveal that only main reduction peak (denoted as A) and its counterpart C are reversible. These two peaks signifies the reduction of copper(II) to copper(I), A, and the subsequent oxidation of copper(I) to copper(II), C. The separations (ca. 80 mV) between peaks A and C, within the scan rates

[‡]Deceased.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of complexes.

employed are characteristics of a quasi-reversible one electron process which is associated with the reduction that probably arises from the relaxation process involved in a stereochemical orientation from planar copper(II) to tetrahedral copper(I)⁸. It has been shown that the formal redox potentials of the copper(II)/copper(I) system are influenced by a number of factors such as coordination number, hard/soft nature of the ligand, stereochemistry, cavity size of the macrocycles and the bulkiness of the ligands⁹. However, due to inherent difficulties in assigning coordination number and stereochemistry of the species present in the solution, the redox process are generally analysed in terms of the nature of the ligands present

there. The present observed E^0 values for the pyrazolyl thiosemicarbazones and dithiocarbazates are indicative of 'hard' nature of the ligand molecules comparable to ligand like ethylenediamine ($E^0 = -0.350$ V), which are likely to be due to the pyrazolyl secondary nitrogen (2N) and azomethine nitrogen donors. Among the series of the complexes the bromo complexes exhibit lower potentials in agreement with previous observations¹⁰. However, change in the attached group to the thiocarbonyl ($>C=S$) function in the ligands do not alter their E^0 value appreciably in the present context but these values are quite close to the other copper(II)/copper(I) couples of similar systems^{6,7}.

Table 1. Cyclic voltammetric data for the copper(II) complexes in DMSO solution containing 0.1 M TBAP on a Pt-electrode at a scan rate 100 mV/s. E values are in volt

Compds.	E_p (A)	E_p (C)	$E_{1/2}^0$	i_{pa}/i_{pc}	E_p (E)	E_p (F)	E_p (G)	E_p (H)	$g_{ }$
[Cu(MPzPyr)Cl]	-0.600	-0.360	-0.480	0.82	+0.310	+0.400	-0.040	+0.260	2.12
[Cu(MPzPyr)Br]	-0.504	-0.240	-0.372	0.86	+0.214	+0.378	—	—	2.14
[Cu(MPzNB)Cl]	-0.529	-0.455	-0.492	0.81	+0.307	+0.267	—	—	2.14
[Cu(MPzNB)Br]	-0.486	-0.342	-0.414	0.94	+0.250	+0.380	—	—	2.10
[Cu(MPzSB-OEt)Cl]	-0.407	-0.372	-0.386	0.86	+0.284	+0.372	-0.132	+0.700	2.16
[Cu(MPzSB)Br]	-0.420	-0.360	-0.390	0.82	+0.310	+0.360	—	—	2.14
[Cu(MPzSB)NO ₃]	-0.400	-0.350	-0.375	0.84	+0.300	+0.350	—	—	2.14
[Cu(MPzSB)ClO ₄]	-0.410	-0.360	-0.380	0.78	+0.320	+0.320	—	—	2.15

The reduction peak E (*ca.* +0.300 V) and its counterpart F (*ca.* +0.380 V) shown in Fig. 1 may correspond to oxidation of the halide associated with the complex species that would only occur after the complete reduction of ligand moiety (it is not observed on the initial scan). Leovac *et al.*¹¹ found that the shapes of cyclic voltammograms for complexes derived from S-alkyl dithiocarbazates were greatly affected by the nature of the supporting electrolyte present in the solution. But no significant changes were observed in the shape of cyclic voltammograms and in E^0 values for the complexes derived from HMPzSB on replacement of supporting electrolyte (e.g. lithium chloride) in place of tetrabutylammonium perchlorate.

The peak G and its corresponding peak H in the cyclic voltammograms of [Cu(MPzPyr)Cl] and [Cu(MPzSB-OEt)Cl] are not quietly explainable but it may be due to reduction of the conjugated portion of the coordinated ligand.

Experimental

The copper(II) complexes were prepared by refluxing the ligand with copper(II) salts in anhydrous ethanol or CH₃CN in the 1 : 1 ratio. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded with the cyclic voltammetry model 270/250 Research Electrochemistry software (Version 4.23) in DMSO solution of the species ($\sim 10^{-3}$ M) using tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (NBu₄ClO₄; 0.1 M) as supporting electrolyte, Pt-electrode as working electrode and standard calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode in the Department of Chemistry, Burdwan University and the scan rate employed was 100 mV/s.

Acknowledgement

Author (PB) is grateful to Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), New Delhi for the financial support during the tenure of the work. The authors are also thankful to Dr. Chittaranjan Sinha of the Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Kolkata, for providing cyclic voltammetric studies.

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